

Nomisma ***Uncertainty and*** ***AMT Vagueness*** **Modelling** **Approaches**

Florian Thiery M.Sc., Dr. Allard
Mees, Dr. Kasten Tolle, Dr.
David Wigg-Wolf

Nomisma.org ... uncertainty

http://nomisma.org/id/uncertain_14_pco

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Quantitative Analysis

uncertain_14_pco (nmo:Mint)

skos:prefLabel Uncertain Mint 14 (en)
skos:definition Uncertain Ptolemaic Mint 14, provincial. (en)
dcterms:isPartOf http://nomisma.org/id/greek_numismatics
dcterms:source http://nomisma.org/id/coins_ptolemaic_empire
rdf:type skos:Concept
skos:changeNote http://nomisma.org/id/uncertain_14_pco#provenance
skos:inScheme <http://nomisma.org/id/>
skos:scopeNote This concept should be used only in the context of Ptolemaic coinage. (en)

Data Provenance ▶

Associated Types (max 10) ▼

[+ View SPARQL for full query](#) [Download CSV](#)

Type

Coins of the Ptolemaic Empire Vol. I, Part II, no. B107

Mint	Uncertain Mint 14
Denomination	Chalkous
Date	294 B.C. - 294 B.C.

Real World - how to handle uncertain data

... but I am not sure, the coin is not well preserved!

uncertainty, ambiguity, accuracy/imprecision, incompleteness, ...

„Veracity“ (or truthfulness - <https://web.archive.org/web/20180731105912/https://spotlessdata.com/blog/big-datas-fourth-v>)
as on V of the Big Data

Modelling solutions for uncertainty ...

- Extra properties
- Reified statements

Triple Explosion!

Defining nm:issuer_uncertain as subproperty of nm:issuer!

**Properties Explosion!
and not very flexible!**

Modelling solutions for uncertainty ...

- Attribute assignment
- Blank scope node

CIDOC CRM / RS Version:

Academic Meta Tool: Quadruple


```
@prefix amt: <http://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab#> .  
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .  
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .  
_:123 rdf:subject amt:Concept .  
_:123 rdf:predicate amt:Role .  
_:123 rdf:object amt:Concept .  
_:123 amt:weight rdfs:Literal .
```

Linked Open Samian Ware: AMT Modelling

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Informationcarrier 118117 can be represented by the potforms 18 OR 15/17 OR 18/31 resulting in a degree of 0.33 for 18.

